

METHANE CYCLE AND SMALL-SCALE WINDS AT SATURN'S MOON TITAN, WITH 2D MESOSCALE MODELLING AND CASSINI/ISS DATA ANALYSIS.

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Titan, Saturn's largest moon, is the only moon in the Solar System to have a substantial atmosphere, composed of 95% of nitrogen and 5% of methane. At the surface, the pressure is 1.5 bar and the temperature is ~94 K. As a result, methane can condense, and form rainfall, rivers, lakes, and seas, making Titan the only body besides Earth to have liquid at its surface. A majority of knowledge about Titan comes from the Cassini-Huygens mission, which studied Saturn's system from 2004 to 2017. Yet, many mysteries remain today. In particular, the atmospheric circulation above the lakes, the energy and mass transfers between the atmosphere and the surface, and the methane cycle in general, remain poorly constrained. The work presented here is in two parts: the first part focuses on 2D modelling of the atmospheric circulation around small lakes, and the second part concentrates on the cloud dynamics in a methane storm, from the study of Cassini/ISS images. We use the mtWRF mesoscale model (Rafkin and Soto 2020, Chatain et al. 2022) to study the effect of surface properties on the wind circulation, atmospheric and lake temperature, and methane evaporation. We focus on small lakes called Sharp-Edged Depressions (SEDs). SEDs are lakes limited by high-elevation terrains called ramparts, that have surface properties different from the surrounding plains. The model domain is 2-D, 1200 km wide with 1 km resolution, and 15 km high with 50 vertical layers. The methane lake is at the center of the model with a diameter of 20 km, and the lake is surrounded by 5 km wide ramparts. We study the effect of the ramparts' surface properties (thermal inertia, surface roughness, emissivity, and albedo). We find that, in the expected range of variation of these parameters, the surface roughness is the parameter with the most significant impact. A higher rampart roughness causes slower horizontal winds close to the surface, less methane evaporation on the lake, and a higher surface temperature at the lake and at the ramparts.

In the second part of this work, we investigate cloud dynamics through the analysis of Cassini/ISS images of a methane storm near Titan's South Pole, observed at the start of the Cassini mission. We use an image analysis software (PLIA, Hueso et al. 2010) and a correlation image software (PICV3, Hueso et al. 2020) to obtain wind measurements tracking the changes in the clouds. We find that image navigation uncertainties produced by the elevated hazes that cover Titan limit the quality of the analysis and we design a procedure to correctly navigate the images using surface features. The aim is to develop a general method to study cloud dynamics from the analysis of Cassini/ISS images. Current results imply low intensity motions associated to this cloud system.

Keywords: Titan, mesoscale modelling, Titan lakes, Cassini/ISS, Titan clouds